

DEVELOPING SPEAKING SKILLS IN ENGLISH LESSONS

Bahora Nurullaeva

Student at Termez University of Economics and Service

G.A.Salamova

Scientific advisor.

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Abstract. The article discusses effective methods for improving speaking skills in English language classes. It focuses on communicative approaches, role plays, group activities, and the use of audio and video materials to enhance students' speaking abilities. Creating opportunities for students to use the language freely and actively participate in communication is essential. The article is based on the research of Uzbek, English, and Russian scholars in this field.

Key words: English language, speaking skills, communicative approach, role plays, group work, audio materials, video materials, language learning, fluency.

РАЗВИТИЕ НАВЫКОВ РАЗГОВОРНОЙ РЕЧИ НА УРОКАХ АНГЛИЙСКОГО
ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. В статье рассматриваются эффективные методы улучшения навыков говорения на уроках английского языка. Основное внимание уделяется коммуникативным подходам, ролевым играм, групповым занятиям и использованию аудио- и видеоматериалов для улучшения навыков говорения учащихся. Создание возможностей для учащихся свободно использовать язык и активно участвовать в общении имеет важное значение. Статья основана на исследованиях узбекских, английских и русских ученых в этой области.

Ключевые слова: английский язык, навыки говорения, коммуникативный подход, ролевые игры, групповая работа, аудиоматериалы, видеоматериалы, изучение языка, беглость.

Introduction. Developing speaking skills is important in the process of learning English. Speaking, one of the most basic communicative skills in a language, plays an important role in successfully mastering the language. Also, communicating fluently in English helps students not only learn the language It helps to master not only grammar and vocabulary, but also conversational culture and the ability to think quickly. In this article, we will analyze the main methods used to develop speaking skills in English lessons.

Skills play an important role in learning English, as it is one of the most widely used and effective tools in the process of language acquisition. To be able to speak English effectively, students must not only master vocabulary and grammar, but also learn to use the language in

practice and express their thoughts clearly. At the same time, the development of speaking skills requires effective methodologies and approaches in language teaching.

Speaking skills not only helps you express yourself clearly and fluently in communication, but also allows you to understand the language more deeply. The teacher's approach, student motivation, exercises and practices are very important in teaching these skills in English lessons.

Analysis of literature on the topic. Uzbek scholars also have their own approaches to teaching English. In particular, Uzbek linguists and methodologists emphasize the need to use various methods in developing speaking skills.

Sh.Yuldasheva, in her work "Communicative Approach to Teaching English", shows the importance of a communicative approach in developing speaking skills . She emphasizes the importance of students' active participation in communication and creating opportunities for free expression. In her opinion, role-playing games and group work are effective methods for developing speaking skills.

In his "Methodology of Teaching English" A.Azizov emphasizes the need to create more opportunities for students to communicate in language learning. In developing speaking skills, he calls on students to participate in the conversational process, to activate the language through questions and answers and conversations.

T.Begimova studies the use of modern technologies and multimedia materials in teaching English . She emphasizes that the use of audio and video materials creates great opportunities for students to improve their pronunciation and develop their skills.

around the world have developed different methods for teaching English. Below we will focus on the opinions of some world scholars.

HG Widdowson, in his book "Teaching Language as Communication", presents the communicative approach as the main method in language teaching. He recommends creating situations similar to real-life communication in order to develop students' speaking skills.

According to Widdowson, in the process of learning a language, students should learn not only grammar, but also how to use language in communication.

D.Nunan, in his work "Language Teaching Methodology", discusses English language teaching methodologies and recommends encouraging students to speak through language games and exercises. He emphasizes that imagination and creative approaches to language learning are the best way to learn a language quickly and effectively.

M.Canale and M.Swain , in their work "Theoretical Bases of Communicative Approaches to Second Language Teaching and Testing", show the importance of communicative competence. They consider it necessary to provide students with the opportunity to participate in various communicative situations and actively communicate in order to develop speaking skills.

Analysis and Conclusion. English speaking skills is to prepare students for practical communication. Frequent speaking practice and expressing opinions in various situations are necessary for students. Such skills, in turn, show that it is not just a matter of knowing the language well, but also its practical application that is important.

speaking skills also helps students become more confident and more fluent in using language. All activities carried out by teachers during the lesson should be aimed at this goal .

Practical Exercises (Practice). The most effective way to develop speaking skills is through practical exercises. Students should learn to apply newly learned grammar and vocabulary in practice. As you teach each new grammar rule or word, involve students in doing exercises based on it. For example, small group or pair discussions, role-playing, debates, and other practical exercises will speed up this process.

Communication Habituation. It is important to provide students with opportunities to regularly communicate in English. The teacher can choose specific topics in the lesson and invite students to make short speeches on this topic. The topics can be in a variety of areas: personal life, students' favorite books, films, dreams, and other topics that interest them and encourage active participation.

Understanding and Applying Grammar. Grammar is the foundation of language, but learning it theoretically is not enough. The interconnectedness of grammar is important in developing speaking skills. Students need to learn to apply grammatical rules and structures in practice. For example, correct use of tenses, word order, sentence structure, and other grammatical aspects must be used effectively in speaking.

Voice and Intonation. Voice and intonation also play an important role in speaking. Speaking in English with correct pronunciation and correct intonation helps students express their thoughts clearly. This, in turn, helps them feel comfortable and confident when speaking.

Didactic Tools and Technology. The use of didactic tools and technology can be effective in developing English speaking skills. Online resources, apps, and training programs offer many interactive exercises that help students develop their speaking skills. For example, students can watch videos and understand how to respond in a given situation.

Engaging Students with Motivation. It is important to help students achieve their goals and encourage them to constantly learn new things. When developing speaking skills, it is important to arouse students' interests and motivate them with unique approaches. Encouraging them to express their thoughts and celebrating every small success is important.

Dialogue and role-playing. An effective way to develop speaking skills in English lessons is to involve students in dialogues and role-playing. Dialogues bring students closer to real-life communication and give them the opportunity to apply the material they have learned in practice.

Role-playing, on the other hand, provides students with the opportunity to express their thoughts freely and use the language frequently. In this way, students learn to speak in different situations and roles, which increases their confidence in communication.

Group work. Another method that is considered effective in developing speaking skills is group work. By encouraging students to divide into small groups and discuss a specific topic or question, they learn to express their thoughts clearly and correctly, as well as to listen to others and approach their opinions with respect. Group work develops students' communication skills and allows them to learn from each other.

Listening and responding exercises. Listening and responding exercises are also important for developing English speaking skills. With this method, students learn not only to express their own thoughts, but also to correctly understand the thoughts of others and respond to them appropriately. This is especially effective in developing the competencies necessary for fluent communication in English.

Topic-based discussions. Organizing topic-based discussions in lessons can also be an effective way to develop speaking skills. By encouraging students to exchange ideas on specific topics, you can increase their vocabulary and fluency in the language. Within the framework of conversations, students learn to express their thoughts clearly and correctly, which significantly improves their speaking skills.

Working with video and audio materials. Using video and audio materials is also an effective method for developing English speaking skills. Students improve their listening and speaking skills by learning the language through films or video materials, hearing different accents and speech styles. At the same time, with the help of audio materials, students have the opportunity to improve their pronunciation.

Conclusion. There are several methods for developing speaking skills in English lessons that help students improve their communicative abilities. Through methods such as dialogue and role-playing, group work, listening and responding exercises, topic-related conversations, and working with video/audio materials, students can develop their language skills. Such methods not only make the language learning process interesting and effective, but also increase students' confidence in the language and facilitate their ability to communicate freely in English.

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